

EARLY DETECTION AND TREATMENT OF FUNGAL DISEASES

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Abstract. Fungal diseases are infectious diseases caused by fungi, which mainly affect the skin, nails, hair and mucous membranes. This article discusses the importance of early detection of fungal diseases, their main clinical symptoms and modern diagnostic methods. Also, antifungal therapy, local and systemic treatment methods used in treatment are analyzed. The results of the study show that early detection of diseases increases the effectiveness of treatment and prevents complications. The article pays special attention to preventive measures, in particular, personal hygiene and strengthening immunity.

Keywords: Fungal diseases, mycosis, early diagnosis, dermatomycosis, candidiasis, antifungal therapy, prevention.

Introduction. Fungal diseases (mycoses) are a group of infectious diseases that develop in the human body under the influence of fungi. They mainly affect the skin, nails, hair, mucous membranes, and in some cases, internal organs. In recent years, the incidence of mycoses has been increasing due to global climate change, decreased immunity, and improper use of antibiotics.

Timely detection and treatment of fungal diseases is very important, because in late cases they can become chronic, significantly reducing the patient's quality of life. The purpose of this article is to shed light on the methods of early detection of fungal diseases and modern treatment approaches on a scientific basis.

Methodology. This article is based on the analysis of scientific literature, and the following methods were used: literature analysis - study of scientific sources in dermatology and microbiology; comparative method - comparison of different treatment methods; generalization of clinical observations - drawing conclusions based on the condition of patients.

The study studied information on modern dermatological and laboratory diagnostic methods.

Results. Main types of fungal diseases: Fungal diseases are divided into the following main types:

Dermatomycoses - skin and hair lesions (ringworm)

Onychomycosis - nail fungus

Candidiasis - lesions of the mucous membranes and internal organs

Systemic mycoses - severe forms affecting internal organs.

Symptoms of the disease and their early detection. Early detection of fungal diseases is carried out by the following signs: redness, itching and peeling of the skin, thickening and

discoloration of the nails, bleached or moist mucous membranes (for example, a white coating in the mouth), hair loss or breakage

Early diagnosis methods: Microscopic examination, laboratory tests (sowing method), dermatological examination, modern methods (PCR diagnostics).

Treatment methods. Treatment of fungal diseases requires an integrated approach:

Topical treatment: antifungal creams and ointments, sprays and solutions.

Systemic treatment: antifungal drugs (in tablet form), immunosuppressants. For example, widely used drugs include Fluconazole and Itraconazole.

Additional measures: strict hygiene, keeping the affected area dry, using personal items separately.

Discussion. Studies show that early detection of fungal diseases significantly increases the effectiveness of treatment. Especially in people with low immunity, mycoses develop quickly and can become complicated.

Improper use of antibiotics also creates conditions for the development of fungi.

Therefore, it is important to take medications only on the recommendation of a doctor.

Many fungal diseases can be prevented by following preventive measures. This reduces the burden on the healthcare system.

Conclusion. Fungal diseases are among the most common infectious diseases and have a negative impact on human health. For their effective control, it is necessary to: early detection of diseases, correct and timely treatment, adherence to preventive measures, and increase the medical literacy of the population.

Early diagnosis and proper treatment can completely eliminate fungal diseases and prevent their complications.

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